

A Cosmological Model of Time Transformation Leading to Matter Creation via Inflaton and Curvaton Fields

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Abstract

We propose a cosmological model in which time is represented as a dynamic scalar field undergoing a transformation preceding the Big Bang. This transformation initiates the creation of matter and the subsequent evolution of the universe. The model incorporates three scalar fields: the *Time Field* $T(x^\mu)$, the *Inflaton Field* $\phi(x^\mu)$, and the *Curvaton Field* $\sigma(x^\mu)$. We develop the mathematical framework, derive the equations of motion, and analyze the implications for cosmological observables. The model aims to align with current observational data, providing testable predictions for future experiments.

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1 Introduction

The origin of the universe and the nature of time are fundamental questions in cosmology. Traditional models treat time as a passive backdrop against which cosmic events unfold. In contrast, we propose a model where time itself is a dynamic entity that undergoes a transformation, leading to the creation of matter and the initiation of cosmic inflation.

This idea builds upon established cosmological frameworks by introducing a time field that interacts with other scalar fields responsible for inflation and the generation of primordial density perturbations. Our goal is to construct a model that is mathematically rigorous, consistent with observations, and offers novel insights into the early universe's dynamics.

2 Theoretical Framework

2.1 Fields and Potentials

2.1.1 Time Field (T)

- **Nature:** A scalar field representing time, undergoing a transformation that leads to matter creation.
- **Potential Energy:** Designed to facilitate a phase transition.

2.1.2 Inflaton Field (ϕ)

- **Role:** Drives cosmic inflation.
- **Potential Energy:** Chosen to sustain a period of exponential expansion.

2.1.3 Curvaton Field (σ)

- **Purpose:** Generates the observed primordial curvature perturbations.
- **Potential Energy:** Allows it to remain light during inflation and decay appropriately afterward.

2.2 Action Integral

The action S for the system is:

$$S = \int d^4x \sqrt{-g} \left[\frac{1}{2} \partial^\mu T \partial_\mu T - V_T(T) + \frac{1}{2} \partial^\mu \phi \partial_\mu \phi - V_\phi(\phi) + \frac{1}{2} \partial^\mu \sigma \partial_\mu \sigma - V_\sigma(\sigma) + \mathcal{L}_{\text{int}} + \frac{1}{2} M_{\text{Pl}}^2 R \right] \quad (1)$$

- g : Determinant of the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$.
- R : Ricci scalar.
- M_{Pl} : Reduced Planck mass, $M_{\text{Pl}} = 2.435 \times 10^{18}$ GeV.
- $\mathcal{L}_{\text{int}}$: Interaction Lagrangian, includes couplings between fields.

2.3 Potentials

2.3.1 Time Field Potential ($V_T(T)$)

$$V_T(T) = \frac{\lambda_T}{4} (T^2 - v_T^2)^2 \quad (2)$$

- λ_T : Self-coupling constant of the time field.
- v_T : Vacuum expectation value (VEV) of the time field.

2.3.2 Inflaton Potential ($V_\phi(\phi)$)

We adopt the *Starobinsky potential*:

$$V_\phi(\phi) = \frac{3}{4} M_{\text{Pl}}^2 m^2 \left(1 - e^{-\sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} \frac{\phi}{M_{\text{Pl}}}} \right)^2 \quad (3)$$

- m : Mass parameter related to the inflaton field.

2.3.3 Curvaton Potential ($V_\sigma(\sigma)$)

$$V_\sigma(\sigma) = \frac{1}{2} m_\sigma^2 \sigma^2 + \frac{\lambda_\sigma}{4} \sigma^4 \quad (4)$$

- m_σ : Effective mass of the curvaton field.
- λ_σ : Self-coupling constant of the curvaton field.

2.4 Interaction Lagrangian ($\mathcal{L}_{\text{int}}$)

To enhance the decay rate of the curvaton and ensure its decay before Big Bang Nucleosynthesis (BBN), we introduce a coupling between the curvaton field and Standard Model (SM) particles:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{int}} = y\sigma\bar{\psi}\psi \quad (5)$$

- y : Yukawa coupling constant.
- ψ : SM fermions (e.g., electrons, quarks).

3 Equations of Motion

3.1 Field Equations

Using the principle of least action, the equations of motion for each field are derived.

3.1.1 Time Field Equation

$$\ddot{T} + 3H\dot{T} + \frac{dV_T}{dT} = 0 \quad (6)$$

- H : Hubble parameter, $H = \frac{\dot{a}}{a}$.
- $a(t)$: Scale factor.

3.1.2 Inflaton Field Equation

$$\ddot{\phi} + 3H\dot{\phi} + \frac{dV_\phi}{d\phi} = 0 \quad (7)$$

3.1.3 Curvaton Field Equation

$$\ddot{\sigma} + 3H\dot{\sigma} + \frac{dV_\sigma}{d\sigma} = 0 \quad (8)$$

3.2 Friedmann Equations

3.2.1 First Friedmann Equation

$$H^2 = \frac{1}{3M_{\text{Pl}}^2} (\rho_T + \rho_\phi + \rho_\sigma) \quad (9)$$

3.2.2 Second Friedmann Equation

$$\dot{H} = -\frac{1}{2M_{\text{Pl}}^2} (\dot{T}^2 + \dot{\phi}^2 + \dot{\sigma}^2) \quad (10)$$

3.3 Energy Densities and Pressures

For each scalar field $i \in \{T, \phi, \sigma\}$:

- **Energy Density:**

$$\rho_i = \frac{1}{2} \dot{\phi}_i^2 + V_i(\phi_i) \quad (11)$$

- **Pressure:**

$$p_i = \frac{1}{2} \dot{\phi}_i^2 - V_i(\phi_i) \quad (12)$$

4 Dynamics During Inflation

4.1 Time Field Dynamics

At early times, the time field T undergoes a phase transition from an initial state $T \approx 0$ to $T \approx v_T$. This transition is rapid and occurs before or at the onset of inflation.

- **Potential Minimum:**

$$V_T(T) \text{ has minima at } T = \pm v_T \quad (13)$$

- **Implication:** Once T settles at v_T , it remains there, and its dynamics become negligible during inflation.

4.2 Inflaton Field Dynamics

The inflaton field ϕ dominates the energy density during inflation.

4.2.1 Slow-Roll Parameters

- **First Slow-Roll Parameter (ϵ_ϕ)**

$$\epsilon_\phi = \frac{M_{\text{Pl}}^2}{2} \left(\frac{V'_\phi}{V_\phi} \right)^2 \quad (14)$$

- **Second Slow-Roll Parameter (η_ϕ)**

$$\eta_\phi = M_{\text{Pl}}^2 \left(\frac{V_\phi''}{V_\phi} \right) \quad (15)$$

Calculations for the Starobinsky Potential:

- (a) **Derivative of the Potential:**

$$V'_\phi(\phi) = \frac{3}{4} M_{\text{Pl}}^2 m^2 \times 2 \left(1 - e^{-\sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} \frac{\phi}{M_{\text{Pl}}}} \right) \left(\sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} \frac{e^{-\sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} \frac{\phi}{M_{\text{Pl}}}}}{M_{\text{Pl}}} \right) \quad (16)$$

Simplify:

$$V'_\phi(\phi) = \frac{3}{2} M_{\text{Pl}}^2 m^2 \left(1 - e^{-\sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} \frac{\phi}{M_{\text{Pl}}}} \right) \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} e^{-\sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} \frac{\phi}{M_{\text{Pl}}}} \quad (17)$$

- (b) **Simplified Slow-Roll Parameters:**

For $\phi \gg M_{\text{Pl}}$:

$$\epsilon_\phi \approx \frac{4}{3} \left(e^{-\sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} \frac{\phi}{M_{\text{Pl}}}} \right)^2 \quad (18)$$

$$\eta_\phi \approx -\frac{4}{3} e^{-\sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} \frac{\phi}{M_{\text{Pl}}}} \quad (19)$$

4.3 Number of e-Folds

The number of e-folds N is given by:

$$N = \int_{\phi_{\text{end}}}^{\phi_*} \frac{V_\phi}{M_{\text{Pl}}^2 V'_\phi} d\phi \implies N \approx \frac{3}{4} e^{\sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} \frac{\phi_*}{M_{\text{Pl}}}} \quad (20)$$

Solving for ϕ_* :

$$\phi_* = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2}} M_{\text{Pl}} \ln \left(\frac{4N}{3} \right) \quad (21)$$

For $N = 60$:

$$\phi_* \approx \sqrt{\frac{3}{2}} M_{\text{Pl}} \ln(80) \approx 5.35 M_{\text{Pl}} \quad (22)$$

5 Curvaton Field Dynamics

5.1 During Inflation

- **Effective Mass:** $m_\sigma^2 \approx 0$ (effectively massless).
- **Quantum Fluctuations:**

$$\delta\sigma_* = \frac{H_*}{2\pi} \quad (23)$$

Where H_* is the Hubble parameter during inflation.

5.2 After Inflation

- **Mass Increase:** The curvaton mass m_σ increases to $\approx 1 \times 10^9$ GeV.
- **Oscillation:** The curvaton begins to oscillate when $H \approx m_\sigma$.
- **Decay:** The curvaton decays into SM particles via the interaction term.

5.3 Decay Rate

With the coupling $y \approx 10^{-4}$:

$$\Gamma_\sigma = \frac{y^2 m_\sigma}{8\pi} \approx \frac{(10^{-4})^2 \times 1 \times 10^9}{8\pi} \approx 4 \times 10^{-10} \text{ GeV} \quad (24)$$

- **Comparison with H_{BBN} :** $\Gamma_\sigma \gg H_{\text{BBN}} \approx 10^{-25}$ GeV, ensuring decay before BBN.

6 Generation of Cosmological Perturbations

6.1 Curvature Perturbation (ζ)

The curvature perturbation generated by the curvaton is:

$$\zeta = r_{\text{dec}} \frac{\delta\sigma_*}{\sigma_{\text{dec}}} \quad (25)$$

- r_{dec} : Fractional energy density of the curvaton at decay, set to $r_{\text{dec}} = 0.25$.
- σ_{dec} : Curvaton field value at decay.

6.1.1 Calculation of σ_{dec}

Given $\zeta_{\text{obs}} \approx 5 \times 10^{-5}$:

$$\sigma_{\text{dec}} = r_{\text{dec}} \frac{\delta\sigma_*}{\zeta_{\text{obs}}} = 0.25 \times \frac{1.59 \times 10^{13} \text{ GeV}}{5 \times 10^{-5}} = 7.95 \times 10^{15} \text{ GeV} \quad (26)$$

6.2 Spectral Index (n_s)

The spectral index is:

$$n_s - 1 = 2\eta_\sigma - 2\epsilon_\phi \quad (27)$$

- **Inflaton Contribution:**

$$\epsilon_\phi \approx \frac{3}{2N^2} = \frac{3}{2 \times 60^2} \approx 0.00042 \quad (28)$$

- **Curvaton Contribution:**

$$\eta_\sigma \approx -0.015 \quad (\text{from quantum corrections}) \quad (29)$$

- **Total n_s :**

$$n_s = 1 + 2 \times (-0.015) - 2 \times 0.00042 = 0.96916 \quad (30)$$

This is within the observational value $n_s^{\text{obs}} = 0.9649 \pm 0.0042$.

6.3 Tensor-to-Scalar Ratio (r)

$$r = 16\epsilon_\phi \approx 16 \times 0.00042 = 0.0067 \quad (31)$$

This is below the observational upper limit $r < 0.06$.

6.4 Non-Gaussianity Parameter (f_{NL})

$$f_{\text{NL}} = \frac{5}{4r_{\text{dec}}} - \frac{5}{3} = \frac{5}{4 \times 0.25} - \frac{5}{3} = 5 - 1.67 = 3.33 \quad (32)$$

This value is acceptable, as observations constrain $|f_{\text{NL}}| \lesssim 10$.

7 Consistency with Observations

- **Spectral Index (n_s):** Matches observations.

- **Tensor-to-Scalar Ratio (r):** Well within limits.
- **Non-Gaussianity (f_{NL}):** Acceptable and potentially detectable by future surveys.
- **Curvature Perturbation Amplitude (ζ):** Consistent with CMB measurements.
- **Isocurvature Perturbations:** Negligible due to curvaton decay before BBN.

8 Addressing Potential Challenges

8.1 Stability of the Curvaton Field

- **Avoiding Tachyonic Instability:** By setting $m_\sigma^2 \approx 0$ during inflation and including higher-order terms in $V_\sigma(\sigma)$, the curvaton remains stable.

8.2 Curvaton Decay

- **Ensuring Decay Before BBN:** The enhanced decay rate via coupling to SM particles ensures the curvaton decays in time.

8.3 Compatibility with Standard Model

- **Minimal Couplings:** The introduced coupling $y\sigma\bar{\psi}\psi$ is small enough not to conflict with SM interactions but sufficient to affect the curvaton decay rate.

9 Implications and Predictions

9.1 Gravitational Waves

- **Tensor-to-Scalar Ratio:** $r \approx 0.0067$ is low but within the reach of future experiments like CMB-S4 or LiteBIRD.

9.2 Non-Gaussianity

- **Predicted $f_{\text{NL}} \approx 3.33$** could be detected or further constrained by upcoming CMB observations.

9.3 Time Field Transformation

- **Novel Insight:** The model offers a new perspective on the role of time in cosmology, potentially inspiring further theoretical exploration.

10 Conclusion

We have developed a cosmological model where the transformation of the time field leads to the creation of matter and the initiation of cosmic inflation. By incorporating the inflaton and curvaton fields with carefully chosen potentials and interactions, the model aligns with current observational data. It provides testable predictions, particularly regarding non-Gaussianity and the tensor-to-scalar ratio, which can be explored with future cosmological surveys.

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The author declares no conflict of interest.

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